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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 7.4 – XR DESIGN GUIDELINES

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Executive summary

Extended Reality (XR) technologies promise improved accessibility and usability for integrating digital technologies in our everyday lives but also work contexts. In THEIA^{XR} we demonstrated its potential to improve interaction with collision avoidance, navigation, and tool movement assistance systems. However, practical guidelines for designing appropriate and useful implementations are still sparse, mainly address non-work applications, and are rather unspecific. In exploring suitable designs of XR in THEIA^{XR} we recognized that a good XR design addresses design dimensions and contextual factors that are missing in existing guidelines.

The presentation of virtual information must align with the operator's cognitive and attentional capacities, as well as with the physical constraints of the working environment. Drawing from our research and development experiences, this work presents a set of implications and design guidelines for effectively integrating XR technologies into off-highway user interfaces. We focus on how XR can balance attention, relevance, and complexity in information presentation while supporting usefulness and operator acceptance. Our framework builds upon a taxonomy of XR applications that consider perceptual immersion, interaction modality, and contextual relevance. From this foundation, we derive principles for managing cognitive load, aligning information with work tasks, and ensuring compatibility with diverse operating conditions.

This deliverable translates our experiences from explorative design iterations and testing into a set of applicable XR design guidelines with practical implications, especially targeting for applications in the off-highway domain, that poses specific challenges for interface design. Off-highway operators, such as those in our use cases of snow grooming, logistics or construction, work under highly variable environmental conditions and perform physically demanding tasks while monitoring complex machine systems. Operators must continuously assess the machine's status, task progress, and environmental factors, while continuously controlling machine functions to reach defined work goals. Efficient use of resources, safety, and precision are key performance criteria that operators must recognize. In these contexts, access to digital information (e.g., navigation guidance, process performance, or production targets) is becoming ever more important. The operation of modern off-highway machinery increasingly depends on data from sensors, automation systems, and remote sources. This is where XR technologies can provide benefits, as they allow for integrating digital information in familiar information perception and processing routines, keeping workload manageable. However, unfamiliar, non-intuitive, too complex or obtrusive ways of augmentation can cause distraction, high workload, and even decrease work performance. Thus, the presented XR design guidelines in this deliverable aim to inform user interface designers to consider important relations between XR design, contextual, and human factors that affect interaction performance and technology acceptance.

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1 Introduction

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This deliverable translates our experiences from explorative design iterations and testing into a set of applicable XR design guidelines with practical implications, especially targeting for applications in the off-highway domain, that poses specific challenges for interface design. Off-highway operators, such as those in our use cases of snow grooming, logistics or construction, work under highly variable environmental conditions and perform physically demanding tasks while monitoring complex machine systems. Operators must continuously assess the machine's status, task progress, and environmental factors, while continuously controlling machine functions to reach defined work goals. Efficient use of resources, safety, and precision are key performance criteria that operators must recognize. In these contexts, access to digital information (e.g., navigation guidance, process performance, or production targets) is becoming ever more important. The operation of modern off-highway machinery increasingly depends on data from sensors, automation systems, and remote sources.

These characteristics lead to unique and dynamic information demands and stringent requirements for how digital information should be presented and interacted with. However, traditional display-based interfaces are not always well suited for this purpose. Operators typically need to keep their focus on the environment rather than on screens, and frequent visual shifts between the real-world scene and digital displays can increase workload, slow response times, and compromise situational awareness. This is where XR technologies can provide benefits, as they allow for integrating digital information in familiar information perception and processing routines, keeping workload manageable. However, unfamiliar, non-intuitive, too complex or obtrusive ways of augmentation can cause distraction, high workload, and even decrease work performance. Thus, the presented XR design guidelines in this deliverable aim to inform user interface designers to consider important relations between XR design, contextual, and human factors that affect interaction performance and technology acceptance.

2 State of the Art on Guidelines and Principles for Extended Reality Interaction

Designing effective XR interfaces faces challenges due to the consideration of multimodality (addressing different information channels), and the blending of real and virtual information that come with the risk that operators may not be able to distinguish one from the other, or even information loss (e.g., concealment of real visual cues by overlaid digital visualizations). Unlike traditional graphical user interfaces (GUIs), XR systems engage the full sensorimotor loop of the user, requiring designers to consider ergonomics, perception, motion, safety, and social context in addition to usability and aesthetics [1][2]. To support consistent and inclusive development, various organizations have published guidelines and standards for XR design. These include platform-specific recommendations (e.g., Microsoft Mixed Reality Toolkit [3], Apple's Human Interface Guidelines for AR [4], Google's ARCore UX Guidelines [5], Meta's Oculus Best Practices [6]), international standards (e.g., ISO 9241 series [7][8], ISO/IEC 18039 [9]), and web-based frameworks such as the W3C WebXR Device API [10] and XR Accessibility User Requirements (XAUR) [11] as well as Developer Guidelines, e.g., the one published by the XR association [12]. These documents already form a broad foundation for designing safe, effective, and accessible XR interactions.

Key design imperatives from these sources comprise:

1. **Human-centred design:** Design around the human capabilities and limitations in mobility, sensory perception, or cognitive processing.
2. **Multimodal robustness:** Combine complementary input and feedback channels to increase reliability and accessibility, but also to address strengths and weaknesses of different perception channels.
3. **Comfort and safety first:** Preserve visual stability, reduce latency, and safeguard physical boundaries before aesthetic considerations.
4. **Accessibility as foundation:** Treat accessibility features as integral, not optional, to ensure equitable participation.
5. **Transparency and trust:** Clearly communicate system state, data usage, and environmental boundaries.
6. **Iterative validation:** Continuously test in real contexts and with diverse populations to capture experiential variability.

The following sections elaborate upon the fundamental ideas behind these fundamental guidelines for XR design.

2.1 Usability and Interaction Heuristics

Design principles from traditional interaction research domains (e.g., HCI – Human Computer Interaction) remain relevant but require adaptation to the augmented and three-dimensional nature of XR. Nielsen's usability heuristics emphasize the importance of visibility of system status, user control, consistency, and error recovery are still relevant in augmented information presentation regardless of the addressed channel [13]. Key usability heuristics also apply to XR technologies.

- XR interfaces should make system states perceivable through multimodal cues such as spatial sound, haptic confirmation, or changes in object illumination.
- Users must be able to infer what virtual objects are interactive and how to act upon them. Because traditional cues such as mouse hover or button outlines are absent, XR designers are recommended to employ signifiers such as subtle animation, proximity-based highlights, or shadow cues to indicate interactivity [3].
- Across modes and contexts build user trust and reduce cognitive load. For instance, similar gestures should have consistent meanings across applications (e.g., pinch to select, grip to grab), and physical metaphors (buttons, sliders, panels) should behave in predictable, physics-based ways.
- Error tolerance and undo mechanisms are crucial given the imprecision of the spatial input and complex information output. XR systems should tolerate input errors, e.g., in hand tracking or spatial positioning. Misalignments or wrong inputs should be easily reversible, e.g., by allowing users to easily reset object positions or recall lost virtual items.

2.2 Spatial Layout and Visual Design

As the main field of research for XR technologies stems from human-computer interaction, existing guidelines heavily address spatially visual augmentation. Spatial XR must accommodate human constraints regarding visual perception.

- According to Microsoft’s Mixed Reality Design Guidelines [3], interactive elements should be positioned within a “comfortable interaction zone” that corresponds roughly to the area users can reach without stretching or turning their heads excessively. Elements that require frequent attention should remain near eye level to minimize fatigue and neck strain.
- ISO 9241-392 recommends maintaining consistent scale cues (e.g., occlusion, shadows, stereoscopic disparity) to preserve depth perception and avoid visual discomfort. Incorrect scaling or floating UI panels can lead to perceptual conflict, contributing to visual fatigue [8]. Designers should ensure that virtual objects appear to occupy plausible spatial relationships with the physical environment.
- Text, icons and graphical representations must remain readable and recognizable at expected distances and under varying lighting conditions. Apple’s AR Human Interface Guidelines emphasize high contrast, minimal clutter, and dynamic adaptation to environmental lighting to preserve legibility [4].
- Positioning digital visual cues should respect environmental affordances and the user’s movement space. Google’s ARCore guidelines recommend anchoring digital objects to real-life surfaces, avoiding occlusion of real-world safety-critical areas, and maintaining spatial stability as the user moves [5].

2.3 Movement and Comfort

Many existing guidelines address motion issues that are especially relevant in highly virtual XR environments. Simulator sickness, for example, arises when visual and vestibular cues of conflict, leading to nausea, disorientation, or fatigue. Meta’s VR design guidelines, supported by research on cybersickness [15], recommend several mitigation strategies:

- Minimize acceleration and forced motion. Locomotion methods should avoid continuous motion that the body does not physically perform. Teleportation, incremental “dash” movement, or arm-swing locomotion can reduce sensory conflict.
- Maintain a stable frame rate. A minimum of 72 Hz (and ideally 90 Hz or higher) prevents visible stutter and reduces motion sickness.
- Reduce latency. Tracking latency between head or hand movement and visual response should remain below 20 ms to preserve a sense of presence.
- Provide user control. Users should be able to adjust comfort settings, e.g., vignetting, snap rotation, or seated vs. standing modes, to accommodate personal sensitivity.
- Additionally, designers should respect physical boundaries. Modern systems use guardian or pass-through modes to warn users when they approach real-world obstacles. Developers should integrate these systems and ensure that virtual experiences do not encourage unsafe movement beyond the defined play area.

2.4 Multimodal Input and Interaction

XR technologies often involve means of adaptability and interactivity. Utilized interaction technologies or techniques include gaze, gesture, and controller inputs, or voice commands. Effective design considers these modalities as complementary rather than redundant. According to the W3C's XR Accessibility User Requirements, systems should support multimodal input so that users can select the most comfortable or accessible method for each task, where varying contextual influences impairs the use of some of these modalities.

- Hand and gesture interactions can be more natural and intuitive but can also imitate interactions with real-world objects better and benefit from affordances resembling physical analogues. Users should see responsive feedback, such as hand outlines, highlights, or haptic pulses, indicating when they can grab or release objects. Because tracking precision varies, interactions should be tolerant to minor deviations and include snapping or magnetic alignment aids.
- Physical controllers remain important for high-precision or force-based interactions. The design should minimize required grip strength and avoid repetitive strain, following ergonomic principles from ISO 9241-410.
- Gaze-based input is especially useful when the user does not have a free hand. However, designers must account for involuntary eye movements and avoid triggering actions solely based on gaze dwell. Combining gaze inputs with a secondary confirmation gesture (e.g., air-tap or voice command) enhances reliability.
- Speech and natural language input enable hands-free control, but must account for environmental noise and privacy concerns. Designers should provide visible feedback when the system is listening and confirm recognized commands.

2.5 Sensory Feedback: Visual, Haptic, and Auditory Cues

XR technologies not also input on different perception channels, but are also capable of outputting feedback on multiple modalities. The combination of visual, haptic, and auditory cues establishes realism and supports situational awareness.

- Visual feedback communicates system state and interaction outcomes. Subtle animations, colour changes, or particle effects can signal successful actions or errors. Designers should avoid excessive motion or flashing to prevent visual fatigue and photosensitive triggers, in line with ISO 9241-391 recommendations.
- Haptic feedback enhances realism and confirmation. Short, consistent vibrations or force cues can indicate contact, grasp, or system of acknowledgment. Where physical haptics are unavailable, designers can substitute pseudo-haptic cues (e.g., resistance simulated through slowed motion or visual deformation). Accessibility guidelines, however, recommend providing equivalent non-haptic cues for users with reduced tactile sensitivity.
- Spatial audio adds orientation and immersion. Sound can convey object location, distance, and state (e.g., a virtual machine humming or a UI element clicking). Microsoft's and Meta's frameworks stress the importance of realistic audio occlusion and attenuation, ensuring that sound sources behave consistently within the spatial scene [3][6]. Moreover, sound cues can serve as accessibility aids for users with limited visual access to content.

2.6 Accessibility and Inclusion

Immersive technologies can exacerbate existing accessibility barriers. The W3C's XR Accessibility User Requirements [11] outlines comprehensive strategies to ensure access for users with diverse sensory, motor, and cognitive abilities. Designers should provide motion-agnostic alternatives for users sensitive to motion sickness or unable to perform gestures. Examples include voice commands, controller buttons, or traditional 2D interface modes. Customizable interaction parameters (e.g., speed, reach distance, text size, and colour contrast) allow adaptation to individual needs. Alternative representations should supplement spatial-only cues. If information is presented through 3D positioning or colour alone, text or audio equivalents should be available. For instance, an AR system that uses distance to encode data should also provide numeric or textual labels. Captioning and transcription are critical for spoken dialogue or environmental audio. Spatial sound should be paired with visual indicators for users with hearing impairments. Finally, input remapping and device flexibility are essential. Users should be able to reassign controls and switch between input methods without losing progress.

2.7 Safety, Privacy, and Well-Being

Immersive environments can obscure awareness of the physical surroundings, creating risks of collision, motion injury, or overexertion. Industry guidelines from the XR Association (XRA, 2023) recommend implementing guardian systems that visualize real-world boundaries and trigger alerts when users approach obstacles. Experiences should encourage users to take regular breaks and allow seamless pausing or exiting to reorient themselves. Another issue regards photosensitive safety, as addressed in ISO 9241-391, which specifies luminance and frequency thresholds to minimize seizure risk. Designers should avoid high-contrast flickering, rapid motion, or patterned textures near critical frequencies (typically 3–30 Hz).

- Privacy and data protection present emerging challenges in XR systems that collect biometric and environmental data, such as eye movements, hand trajectories, voice input, or room mapping as part of their technical functions. These data can reveal sensitive information. Designers must obtain explicit consent, provide clear data usage explanations, and comply with privacy regulations such as the GDPR. Transparency indicators, e.g., visual cues showing when sensors are active, enhance user trust.
- Social and psychological well-being is especially affected in highly immersive XR environments. Prolonged immersion may induce dissociation or reduced situational awareness, while avatars and virtual embodiments raise questions of identity and representation. Providing debriefing screens, time tracking, and content warnings can support healthy usage patterns.

2.8 Onboarding, Learning, and Discoverability

Because XR interaction is often unfamiliar, designers should evaluate if on-boarding experiences that help users build mental models, are required. Best practices emphasize progressive disclosure that involves introducing core concepts gradually rather than overwhelming users at the start. Tutorials should allow safe exploration and immediate feedback. For instance, Microsoft's HoloLens "bloom" gesture tutorial places users in a simple, forgiving environment where errors have minimal consequences. Providing a "practice mode" accessible at any time enables reinforcement of learned gestures. Also, contextual assistance such as ghosted hand hints, voice prompts, or interactive tooltips helps users recall gestures without breaking immersion. Tutorials should also include accessibility information, e.g., how to enable subtitles, comfort settings, or controller alternatives, so users can configure experiences to their needs.

3 XR Design Guidelines for Off-Highway Machines

Designing effective, appropriate and responsible XR systems requires to consider a multi-perspective view. That means integrating task-based requirements, contextual constraints, physiologic and psychologic ergonomics, as well as ethical, legal and social aspects. Our guidelines aim to specify and extend the state of the art in applicable XR guidelines as represented by industry platforms, standards bodies, and research literature. In developing functional XR concepts for enhanced machine operation in off-highway applications, we recognized that existing guidelines and standards provide a fair guidance for developing usable, safe, and inclusive XR systems that are usable, safe, and inclusive but lack specific tools and design measures. Based on our explorative and user-integrative development procedure, we selected and elaborated on six components of XR design that we found to be important in the off-highway application:

1. Recognize task-based attention allocation profiles
2. Balance obtrusiveness of XR information
3. Balance information complexity
4. Account for XR Technology-Related Limitations
5. Balance Virtuality
6. Consider Adaptability of XR Information

3.1 Recognize task-based attention allocation profiles

Extended Reality (XR) systems for off-highway applications must recognize that the user's primary task usually lies outside the graphical user interface itself. In these contexts, display interactions may come with the risk of competing for attention, potentially reducing performance or compromising safety. XR design should therefore aim to minimize the duration and frequency of explicit display interactions, and instead augment visual, haptic and audio cues operators usually rely on when conducting work procedures. Whereas machine operators in our use cases (snow groomer, reach stacker and excavator operation) mainly focus on the environment, the tool or the machine's overall behavior, involving different visual, haptic and audio cues, attention allocation highly depends on tasks and situations. Therefore, designing effective XR solutions is not only about selecting important information and appropriate presentation forms but should also be based upon a good understanding of the operator's work procedures involving the assessment of attention allocation sequences. Evaluating attention allocation can involve empirical measures such as eye-tracking, head movement analysis, or secondary-task performance. By quantifying the proportion of time users spend attending XR elements, designers can refine when and how information is presented. In this sense, effective XR interaction is characterized less by immersion for its own sake and more by attentional harmony with real-world task performance.

Practical implications:

- Evaluate task and situation-based attention sequences including time spend on defined cues and overall shares of attention allocation on (e.g. the environment, the display terminal, the haptic controls)
- Limit complexity of XR information and interaction based on the time operators usually spend at the respective location or device
- Align information placement with natural lines of sight to avoid head or eye reorientation, considering what objects operators may focus during certain tasks and situations
- Reduce dependency on display terminals, if possible, to reduce distraction from outside the operator's attentional focus
- Consider attention-aware triggering, so XR information appears only when attention is applied to the respective location or device (e.g., detected by eye tracking or robust predictive task or situation models)

- When operation involves using hardware controls most of the time, consider implementing interaction with the XR presentation directly on the hardware controls or use less disruptive interaction techniques, such as (automation, gaze-based confirmation, proximity sensing, or speech interaction)
- Design for interruption tolerance, ensuring operators can safely ignore XR content that may lay outside their current attentional focus without impairments for work performance and safety

3.2 Balance obtrusiveness of XR information

Machine operators are trained to detect specific cues (e.g., objects, alignments of tool geometry and environment or vibration signatures) in their work routines. Augmenting these cues can easily alienate them, impairing their detection or effectiveness. Therefore, when augmenting important cues, the chosen design of the XR information should preserve the significant signature of the respective cue. The additional layers of information that may come with XR technologies can conceal such cues and completely render detectability impossible. Cognitive load theory supports this approach: when irrelevant or excessive information competes for working memory, task performance declines [16]. Hence, XR feedback should act as a situational cue rather than a constant focal object. This is especially critical for projection-based or display-based augmentations, where visual clutter or misaligned overlays can obscure essential real-world cues.

The principle of non-obtrusiveness emphasizes that digital augmentation should blend seamlessly into the perceptual and task context without unnecessarily dominating attention or altering cue perception, at least for key information cues. To make XR information unobtrusive, designers should be aware of such pivotal cues that are unique for specific tasks, situations, and machines. A systematic analysis of information used in real machine operation scenarios is recommended to inform appropriate XR designs, spatial placement, visual salience, and temporal persistence. Augmented cues should appear where they are most meaningful, but when co-located with the physical elements they reference, they should avoid altering the resulting appearance too much. Minimalist design techniques, such as subtle colour coding, low-opacity overlays, or amplifying cues that preserve the significant cue characteristics and patterns significant for identification, can convey essential data without overwhelming or alienating the visual scene. In haptic and auditory domains, non-obtrusiveness may translate to signals that are perceivable but not startling, e.g., through using gentle, graded vibrations or ambient tones rather than abrupt stimuli that may drown down the original cue. Evaluation of obtrusiveness can include testing for detection of accuracy and performance, subjective workload ratings, visual clutter assessments, and measures of visual attention distribution.

Practical implications:

- Evaluate important cues in specific machine operation tasks and situations including cue location, significant patterns and conditions of occurrence that operators use to reason upon key performance criteria and safety
- Use XR designs that either avoid covering these cues or alienate important cue characteristics or apply augmentations that carefully preserve these characteristics, so they remain detectable and interpretable
- Avoid signal cluttering through too much or interfering information presentations, e.g. by spatially separating XR content from critical real-world features
- Avoid cue concealment, e.g., by using minimal invasive information mappings, e.g., by using simple shapes, outlines, or icons instead of text-heavy overlays, low-saturation colors and transparency by default, increasing salience only when urgency rises, avoid persistent overlays and instead prefer event-based or transient cues that fade automatically
- Consider using peripheral cues (e.g., subtle highlights or halos) when directly augmenting main information streams shows negative effects on information and pattern detection

3.3 Balance information complexity

Depending on the task and situation, processing of real cues in machine operation can already involve high information complexity and mental load. Adding additional information through XR technologies can increase cognitive load, slow decision-making, and impair operation performance. Thus, XR information presentations must balance informativeness with cognitive manageability. Determining the appropriate granularity of information is therefore highly dependent on situative conditions.

An effective approach to align complexity with task criticality and user capabilities requires iterative evaluation grounded in task analysis and user expertise. Especially, in situations with intense information complexity, XR technologies should apply simple, familiar and intuitive forms of information presentation that reduce additional cognitive costs in perceiving and interpreting them by the operators. For instance, trends or anomalies can be represented through colour gradients or motion cues rather than raw numerical data. Similarly, haptic or light feedback can summarize system states through recognizable patterns rather than complex sequences. Empirical evaluation of complexity can involve cognitive workload measures, subjective usability ratings, and performance outcomes. Each additional element in the XR environment must justify its presence by demonstrably improving situational understanding or task efficiency.

Practical implications:

- Match information granularity to situative overall information complexity
- Avoid numerical and text-based presentations and consider using visual equivalents instead
- Present aggregated means of information instead of multiple independent indicators
- Consider preferring compound and abstract visuals using lines, outlines and grids instead of complex 3D models that may require training over completely self-explaining presentations to reduce complexity
- Practice awareness towards concurrent XR elements that must not exceed a cognitively manageable set
- Use hierarchical information structures, where details are revealed only on demand.

3.4 Account for XR Technology-Related Limitations

Despite rapid technological progress, XR systems remain constrained by hardware, sensing, and perceptual limitations. These include limited field of view (especially in optical see-through displays), latency in tracking and rendering, signal resolution, imprecise spatial registration, and varying quality of haptic or light feedback. Such limitations influence how information can be presented. XR technology design should mediate perception rather than perfectly replicate reality.

Effective design strategies focus on error tolerance and perceptual compensation. Visual anchors, shadows, or outlines can help users interpret spatial relationships even when registration is imperfect. Predictive algorithms can preempt small delays in tracking, smoothing movement trajectories. When haptic feedback is coarse, it can be enhanced in realism through multimodal reinforcement, for example, pairing weak vibrations with synchronized visual cues. From an evaluation perspective, documenting technological constraints is crucial to interpret study outcomes accurately. Performance or usability issues may arise not from conceptual flaws but from current hardware limits. In practice, accounting for technological limitations means designing within the envelope of reliable system behaviour, prioritizing stability and clarity over speculative fidelity.

Practical implications:

- Design content that remains legible under variable lighting, dust, vibration, and motion
- Avoid reliance on precise spatial registration for safety-critical information.

- Use redundant cues (visual + auditory or haptic) to compensate for tracking loss or occlusion
- Anticipate latency by avoiding interactions requiring tight temporal precision
- Optimize graphics for limited field of view and resolution
- Ensure seamless degradation when sensors, tracking, or connectivity fail

3.5 Balance Virtuality

Drawing from Milgram and Kishino's (1994) "reality–virtuality continuum" [17], effective XR interaction finds equilibrium between immersion and situational grounding. XR research tends to discuss design topics on applications that apply high levels of virtuality while implementing necessary real-world cues. XR enhanced machine operation instead requires technologies that maintain a clear perception of the real environment, only augmented by useful virtual or digital information. Whereas immersiveness in virtual worlds is a key criterion in virtual-heavy applications, XR technologies in machine operation should aim for reality, although the perception is virtually enhanced. Thus, balancing virtuality refers to managing the degree to which virtual elements dominate, supplement, or coexist with real-world perception. Excessive virtual dominance can detach users from physical context, leading to loss of spatial awareness, and impair operators in applying familiar perception and interpretation routines.

On a practical level, balancing virtuality involves calibrating opacity, immersion level, and sensory blending. Virtual content should appear integrated with physical objects and should avoid masking real-world cues. Psychologically, balanced virtuality supports presence with enhanced information availability without splitting awareness. Cognitive ergonomics research suggests that moderate immersion levels maximize performance for tasks requiring real-world coordination, whereas full immersion may be appropriate for training or simulation contexts [18]. Empirical evaluation can consider real-world presence scales, situational awareness metrics, and subjective comfort. Adjusting visual fidelity, audio realism, or feedback intensity provides practical levers to fine-tune virtuality. The design goal is to ensure that the degree of virtual engagement serves the task's cognitive and physical demands without overwhelming or isolating the user.

Practical implications:

- Prefer augmentation to replacement of real-world perception
- Use XR to enhance interpretation (e.g., highlighting, prediction) rather than replicating physical instruments
- Avoid fully virtual representations when direct perception is available and reliable
- Adjust the degree of virtuality based on environmental uncertainty (e.g., poor visibility)
- Support smooth transitions between low and high virtuality modes
- Clearly distinguish virtual elements from real-world objects to avoid misinterpretation
- Validate that virtual elements do not reduce trust in real-world sensory cues

3.6 Consider Adaptability of XR Information

Machine operation is a dynamic context where user states, environmental conditions, and task priorities continuously change. Accordingly, information requirements regarding what information is needed and what form of presentation is appropriate highly depend on tasks and situations. Static presentation of information risks either under-informing or overloading the user. Therefore, adaptability, the capacity of XR information to adjust timing, modality, and detail, is central to sustaining usability and relevance. In highly dynamic contexts, XR technologies should be able to modulate their behaviour through adaptivity, based on contextual sensing (e.g., task, danger, workload) or adaptability by enabling user input (manual settings, preferences). As accurate models that are required for adaptive functionalities can be very difficult to integrate, enabling the operator to adjust means of XR information presentation can already improve effectiveness, usefulness and acceptance of XR technologies.

Tasks and situations differ in scope, complexity, importance, or urgency resulting in diverging requirements towards the augmented information picture provided by the machines. XR technologies come with many design dimensions that can be altered to match these dynamic requirements. These design dimensions include level of detail, complexity, virtuality, salience, or location of presentation. Adaptability requires suitable means of interactivity, which can come with additional complexity. However, enabling operators to adapt XR features to their actual needs and capabilities can improve usefulness and acceptance of XR technologies.

Practical implications:

- Allow operators to customize XR features but limit interactivity to effective functions to avoid unnecessary increase of interface complexity
- Consider adaptability of the level of detail of the augmenting information to control complexity and task or situation related appropriateness
- Consider adaptability of the level of virtuality to ensure the operator can perceive an undisturbed information picture of the real environment
- Consider adaptability of the position and modality of additional virtual information, enabling the operator to overlay focused areas or controls with important information and to select what information shall take use of the limited peripheral perception capabilities
- Allow users to temporarily suppress or dim XR content during demanding task moments

4 Summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive set of design guidelines for Extended Reality (XR), with a specific focus on off-highway machine operation. Building on existing XR standards and human–computer interaction principles, it addresses the issue that current guidelines are rather generic and insufficiently address requirements of work contexts. Off-highway operators work in dynamic, safety-critical environments with high cognitive and physical load, making traditional display-based XR interfaces problematic.

Based on the iterative design process applied in THEIA^{XR} six key XR design principles for off-highway applications are presented: aligning XR with task-based attention allocation, minimizing obtrusiveness, balancing information complexity, accounting for technological limitations, balancing virtuality with real-world perception, and ensuring adaptability. Across these principles, the emphasis is on supporting situational awareness, reducing workload, preserving critical real-world cues, and enabling flexible, multimodal, and user-adjustable interaction. These guidelines aim to help designers create XR systems that enhance performance, safety, usability, and acceptance in complex industrial work environments.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

[3D]	Three-dimensional
[AR]	Augmented Reality
[GUI]	Graphical User Interface
[HCI]	Human-computer Interaction
[IEC]	International Electrotechnical Commission
[ISO]	International Organization for Standardization
[UI]	User Interface
[VR]	Virtual Reality
[W3C]	World Wide Web Consortium
[XAUR]	XR Accessibility User Requirements
[XR]	Extended Reality